

INTRODUCTION OF DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF THE HIGHER SCHOOL

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Annotation: The article considers the main provisions of the theory of distance learning. Particular attention is paid to the development of information and training technologies in order to create program and methodological materials. The paper formulates the basic principles on the basis of which distance learning systems for students are created.

Keywords: distance learning, information and learning technologies, differentiation and individualization of the learning process, informatization of education.

At present, when educational institutions have gained access to the information resources of the World Wide Web, the use of information and communication technologies in teaching has become a reality, teachers are paying more and more attention to the effectiveness of using new information and computer technologies in the educational process.

The creation of a distance education system became possible with the advent of computer multimedia tools, technologies and high-speed telecommunications networks. A unified way of presenting information of any kind, the possibility of open access to databases, the rapid processing of large amounts of information became the basis for creating a global information and educational space, gave distance education such qualities as openness, focus on the interests of the individual, flexibility of individualized learning.

The technologies used in distance learning are technologies based on the wide application of developmental learning methods, problem-based and research methods, combined with the maximum use of achievements in the field of information technology.

Trends in the development of education based on new progressive concepts, the introduction of the latest pedagogical technologies and scientific and methodological achievements into the educational process, and the creation of a new system of information support for education have led to the spread of a new learning technology - distance education.

Information technologies used in distance learning can be divided into three groups:

- technologies for presenting educational information;
- technologies for the transfer of educational information;
- technologies of storage and processing of educational information.

Together, they form distance learning technologies. At the same time, in the implementation of educational programs, technologies for the transfer of educational information are of particular importance, which, in essence, provide the learning process and its support.

The basis of the learning process is always the transfer of information from the teacher to the student . In this sense, any technology used in education can be called information technology. On the other hand, the term "information technology" is often used in relation to all technologies based on the use of computer technology and telecommunications. To avoid misinterpretation, we define three concepts that are of paramount importance for distance education:

- educational information;
- educational technologies;
- information Technology.

Educational information is the knowledge that must be transferred to the student in order for him to be able to perform this or that activity competently.

In the disciplinary model of education inherent in the full-time education system, the teacher acts as an interpreter of knowledge. In distance learning, the interpreter is to a greater extent the student himself, and therefore, the quality of educational information and the methods of its presentation should be subject to

increased requirements. First of all, this applies to newly created electronic textbooks, as well as to information bases and knowledge banks, reference and expert systems used for educational purposes. The information presented in them, unlike printing, should have a completely different organization and structure. This is due to both the psychophysiological characteristics of the perception of information on a computer screen, and the technology of access to it.

Educational information should not be accumulated in only one or a few places. Its distribution should have an island character, so as to provide the maximum possible access for students to it from any remote places, without a significant increase in the load of telecommunication channels. Large libraries and scientific and educational centers created on the basis of leading universities can become such islands (centers) of information.

Educational technologies are a set of didactic methods and techniques used to transfer educational information from its source to the consumer and depend on the form of its presentation.

A feature of educational technologies is the outstripping nature of their development in relation to technical means. The fact is that the introduction of computer technology in education leads to a revision of all components of the learning process. In the interactive environment "student - computer - teacher" much attention should be paid to the activation of imaginative thinking through the use of technologies that activate the right hemisphere, synthetic thinking. And this means that the presentation of educational material should reproduce the thought of the teacher in the form of images. In other words, the main point in the educational technologies of distance learning is the visualization of thoughts, information, knowledge.

The educational technologies most suitable for use in distance learning include:

- video lectures;
- multimedia lectures and laboratory workshops;
- electronic multimedia textbooks;

- computer training and testing systems;
- simulation models and computer simulators;
- consultations and tests using telecommunications;
- videoconferencing.

Information technologies are hardware and software tools based on the use of computer technology that provide storage and processing of educational information, its delivery to the student, interactive interaction with the teacher or pedagogical software, as well as testing the student's knowledge.

In the educational process, it is not information technology in itself that is important, but the extent to which its use serves to achieve the actual educational goals. The choice of means of communication should be determined by content, not technology. This means that the choice of technologies should be based on a study of the content of training courses, the degree of necessary activity of students, their involvement in the learning process, specific goals and expected learning outcomes, etc. The result of training does not depend on the type of communication and information technologies, but on the quality of development and delivery of courses.

When choosing technologies, it is necessary to take into account the greatest correspondence of some technologies to the characteristic features of the trainees, the specific features of specific subject areas, and the prevailing types of training tasks and exercises.

The main role played by telecommunication technologies in distance learning is to provide educational dialogue. Learning without feedback, without constant dialogue between the teacher and the student is impossible. Learning (as opposed to self-education) is a dialogic process by definition. In full-time education, the possibility of dialogue is determined by the very form of organization of the educational process, the presence of a teacher and a student in the same place at the same time. In distance learning, the educational dialogue must be organized using telecommunication technologies.

Communication technologies can be divided into two types - on - line and offline. The former provide real-time information exchange, that is, a message sent by the sender, upon reaching the recipient's computer, is immediately sent to the appropriate output device. When using off - line technologies, received messages are stored on the recipient's computer. The user can view them with the help of special programs at a convenient time for him. Unlike full-time education, where the dialogue is conducted only in real time (on - line), in DL it can also go in a delayed mode (off - line).

The main advantage of off - line technologies is that they are less demanding on computer resources and communication line bandwidth. They can be used even when connected to the Internet via dial-up lines (in the absence of a permanent connection to the Internet).

Technologies of this kind include e-mail, mailing lists, and teleconferencing. With the help of the list -server, distribution of educational information can be organized, personal communication between the teacher and the student is established with the help of e-mail, and the teleconference allows organizing a collective discussion of the most complex or difficult issues of the course. All of these technologies allow messages to be exchanged between different computers connected to the Internet .

An important advantage of off - line technologies is a large selection of software for working with e-mail and teleconferencing. Modern email programs allow you to send messages in hypertext format (i.e., with hyperlinks, font and color highlighting of text fragments, inserting graphics, etc.). In addition, a file of any format can be attached to the letter, which makes it possible to send, for example, documents in MS format word . The effectiveness of off - line technologies is manifested in the organization of current consultations, current control on the basis of control and independent work, checked "manually" by the teacher.

From on - line technologies, first of all, it should be noted chat , which allows real-time text messaging over the Internet . In the simplest case, a

"conversation" takes place between two users. For a collective conversation, you need to connect to a special server - an IRC server. Then, when working, the user sees a screen in front of him, on which messages are displayed, indicating who sent this message. Most programs also allow you to call one of the users present to a "private" dialogue, closed from other users. The effectiveness of on - line technologies is especially high when organizing network seminars and group consultations.

When organizing joint educational programs, distance learning network technologies are of particular importance, since they allow the most complete implementation of the principle of distribution of educational resources and human resources.

Thus, when using information technologies and means of telecommunications in distance learning, new aspects arise regarding the goals and content of training, organizational forms and methods of educational work. Among the specific factors of distance learning forms and methods, the following can be distinguished:

- changing the content and forms of teaching traditional disciplines when using computer textbooks, multimedia technologies and information materials on the Internet, hosted on WWW servers;
- inclusion in the curricula of new disciplines related to the study of information and telecommunication technologies and applications based on them as tools of knowledge in applied areas of human activity;
- the emergence of new forms of independent search and research work of students, involving the use of global computer networks and distributed databases in the course of educational and research work;
- training students in methods of collective problem solving using Groupware technologies (e-mail, teleconferences, news groups, mailing lists, interactive messaging Chat , whiteboard Board , audio and video conferencing on the Internet and ISDN, corporate Intranet systems, etc.);
- a combination of methods of group and individual work of

students in the classroom when working in local and global computer networks;

- organization of joint work of teachers of various disciplines (possibly from different universities or different countries) at the stages of designing and implementing inter-departmental and inter-university curricula;
- preparation of teachers to work with new methods and organizational forms of education, to the intensive use of network communications and new information technologies in the educational process.

Based on the foregoing, an academic discipline based on distance learning forms and methods can be defined as a specific educational and methodological complex, including computer, telecommunications, methodological and organizational components of a single educational process taking place in several geographically separated training groups with the participation of several teachers, possibly, from different universities.

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